

Enhancing Smiles: Esthetic Transformation with Porcelain Laminate Veneers and Monolithic Zirconia Crowns.

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Abstract:

This article presents a case report focusing on the aesthetic correction of upper anterior spacing using porcelain laminate veneers, and replacement of lower incisors with monolithic zirconia crowns. A 19-year-old patient presented with concerns regarding the noticeable space between her upper front teeth and the desire to improve the appearance of her smile. After thorough examination and treatment planning, a multidisciplinary approach was employed. Which includes the placement of custom porcelain laminate veneers to achieve a harmonious and natural look. Simultaneously, the missing lower incisors were restored by using monolithic zirconia crowns, providing both aesthetic enhancement and functional stability. The treatment approach and outcomes demonstrate the effectiveness of combining advanced dental techniques to address complex aesthetic and functional concerns. Ultimately resulting in a confident and radiant smile for the patient.

Keypoints: PLV'S- Porcelain Laminate Veneers, Monolithic Zirconia, Aesthetics, Smile Designing, All ceramic Restoration.

Introduction:

The esthetic appearance of the smile plays a crucial role in an individual's self-confidence and overall well-being. Dental anomalies such as spacing in the upper anterior teeth and missing lower incisors can significantly impact both the aesthetics and function of the dentition. In recent years, advancements in cosmetic dentistry have provided patients with innovative solutions to address such concerns effectively [1-3]. PLV's have emerged as a popular choice for addressing such concerns, offering a minimally invasive and aesthetically pleasing solution. Additionally, the restoration of missing incisors presents unique challenges, necessitating careful consideration of both functional and aesthetic factors [4]. By presenting a detailed case report of a patient undergoing aesthetic correction of upper anterior spacing and replacement of lower incisors this report aims to highlight the effectiveness of combining advanced dental techniques to achieve a harmonious and natural smile with form and function of the dentition.

Case report:

A 19-year-old female patient presented to the Department of Prosthodontics at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur, citing concerns about missing teeth and aesthetic issues arising from spacing in the maxillary anterior region. Upon review of her medical history, no relevant medical conditions were noted. Dental history revealed the recent extraction of an over-retained deciduous lower right central incisor (41) three months prior. No abnormalities were detected during both extraoral and intraoral examinations. A comprehensive clinical examination included a full functional occlusal assessment, encompassing evaluation of the incisal level of adjacent teeth, as well as the inclination of all anterior teeth and the type of occlusion. Examination revealed spacing between the maxillary incisors (11, 12, 21, 22), with the mandibular right and left central incisors (31, 41) missing.

Treatment planning:

The available treatment options included removable partial denture, fixed partial denture, implants in the mandibular arch, and orthodontic treatment or aesthetic correction with porcelain laminate veneers in the maxillary arch. Due to limited inter-dental space for accommodating two implants, implant placement in the mandibular arch was ruled out. The removable partial denture option was disregarded as the patient expressed unwillingness towards it. Consequently, a fixed partial denture with a four-unit monolithic zirconium bridge

in the mandibular arch was planned. Given the patient's preference for immediate aesthetic improvement without extensive orthodontic treatment, porcelain laminate veneers were picked-out to enhance the aesthetics in the maxillary arch, along with the placement of a full-coverage four-unit monolithic zirconium bridge in the mandibular arch.

Diagnostic wax-up

Pre-operative extraoral photographs (Figure 1) and intraoral photographs (Figure 2) were captured to document the initial presentation. Diagnostic impressions were then obtained, and study models were meticulously prepared. Subsequently, mock-up preparation and diagnostic wax-up procedures were conducted (Figure 3) for both the maxillary and mandibular arches, aiding in the comprehensive treatment planning process.

Intra oral preparations

After duplicating the diagnostic wax-up cast, a putty index (Zhermack Badia Polesine (RO), Italy) was created to serve as a guide for selective tooth preparation (figure 4). Prior to preparation, appropriate shade selection was meticulously performed to achieve optimal aesthetic outcomes.

For laminates preparation, a three-tiered, self-limiting depth cutting diamond (DM 305, Mani, Tochigi, Japan), orientation and depth grooves were prepared (figure 5), with three grooves each measuring 0.5 mm in depth. Subsequently, these grooves were marked using a graphite lead pencil to provide guidance for labial preparation. The remaining enamel was reduced to the level of depth cuts (figure 6) using a tapered round diamond (TR 13, Mani, Tochigi, Japan). Interproximal reduction extended into the embrasure area to ensure the margin between the veneer and unprepared tooth was concealed for improved aesthetics. Incisal reduction incorporated palatal wrap with a mini-chamfer, while the labioincisal and linguoincisal line angles were rounded. The finish line was equigingival to maintain aesthetics. Overall preparation was refined using TR13 F and TR 13 EF (Mani, Tochigi, Japan) to ensure precise preparation (figure 7). Lastly, following the principles of tooth preparations, mandibular abutments were prepared to receive full coverage restoration.

Provisional restoration

Temporary restorations were fabricated using tooth-colored acrylic resin, Oratemp C&B (Prevest DenPro, USA), employing an indirect technique with a putty index derived from the diagnostic wax-up cast. These restorations were then bonded using Oratemp NE (Prevest DenPro, USA) adhesive (Figure 8), effectively serving as provisional restorations for both the maxillary and mandibular arches. These restorations were kept for a week to evaluate patient's compliance and soft tissue response.

Impression making

A week later, the provisional restorations were carefully removed, and thorough evaluation of abutment and soft tissue response was conducted. Prior to the final impression, all abutments and preparations were meticulously finished using finishing diamonds, and gingival retraction cord (UltraPak #000; Ultradent, UT, USA) was placed, accompanied by a gingival hemostatic agent (viscostat clear, Ultradent) to ensure optimal tissue management (figure 9). The final impression was then recorded using a single-step impression technique with light body and putty, polyvinylsiloxane impression materials (Zhermack Badia Polesine (RO), Italy) and evaluated for accurate details of the prepared teeth and surrounding tissues. Subsequently, the master cast was dispatched to the ceramic laboratory, accompanied by detailed instructions, for the fabrication of the prostheses, ensuring precise replication of the planned restorations.

Evaluation and Cementation of final restoration

Initially, a full crown bridge was placed in the anterior mandibular region and carefully assessed for proper margin adaptation and complete seating of the restoration. Subsequently, the bridge was luted using a dual-cure resin (Fusion Ultra D/C, Prevest den pro, USA). For the porcelain laminate veneers, a bisque trial was conducted followed by glazing, before the final placement of the prosthesis. The internal surface of the restoration was prepared by etching with 10% hydrofluoric acid (Angelus Londrina, Brazil) for 90 seconds (figure 10), followed by thorough washing under running water and air drying. A silane coupling agent (Angelus Londrina, Brazil) was then applied for one minute and air dried (Figure 11). On the prepared tooth, a total etching technique was performed using 37% phosphoric acid for 30 seconds (Figure12), followed by washing with water and complete drying of the enamel

surface. Subsequently, a bonding agent was applied and cured with an LED light for 30 seconds (Figure13). The luting agent (Variolink Veneer, Ivoclar Vivadent) was applied to the internal surface of the restoration, and it was positioned on the dentate substrate with light digital pressure. The veneers were placed sequentially on teeth 11, 21, 12 and 22 simultaneously. Excess cement was removed before curing, and then the veneers were initially cured for 10 seconds (Figure 14). Any remaining excess resin residue was removed using manual tools, and the veneers were further cured for 90 seconds using an LED light on the facial and palatal aspects.

Finishing and polishing restoration

Following curing, the restoration underwent meticulous finishing and polishing procedures. First, gross excess resin was carefully removed using hand instruments, ensuring that the restoration's contour was in harmony with the surrounding dentition. Additionally, attention was paid to ensure that the margins were well-sealed and free of any excess cement or roughness. Upon completion of the finishing and polishing procedures, the restoration was evaluated for its overall aesthetics, fit, and function.

Discussion:

A midline diastema, or gap between the front teeth, can be a source of insecurity for many individuals. While some embrace their unique smile, others seek treatment to close the gap and achieve a more harmonious appearance. One popular solution in cosmetic dentistry is the use of porcelain laminate veneers [5]. Porcelain laminate veneers are thin shells of porcelain custom-made to fit over the facial surface of teeth. They are a versatile option for enhancing the aesthetics of the smile, and they offer several advantages for addressing the midline diastema closure. One of the primary benefits of porcelain laminate veneers is their ability to close gaps between teeth with minimal invasion. Unlike traditional orthodontic treatments, which may require months or even years to achieve desired results, veneers offer a relatively quick and efficient solution. In cases where a specific aesthetic concern in anterior region are expected, the diagnostic wax mock-up enables customised planning and a predictable result[6]. A successful treatment depends on proper diagnosis and treatment plan, which will help in determining the best possible options amongst, direct or indirect composite resin, and indirect ceramic laminate veneer selection. The clinician should also analyse the socioeconomic condition of the patient[7]. In the present case report, considering patient's

age, the options presented to the patient was orthodontic treatment but patient was not ready to pursue orthodontic treatment due to the lengthy process and the need for immediate aesthetic results. Also, the orthodontic treatment was avoidable in this case because the diastema was evenly spread. Her prime requisite was that the diastemas to be closed rapidly with long-term aesthetic benefits[8]. Success of PLV's depends on patient's selection, as in this case, the patient was selected for a conservative treatment plan because of her young age also as the mandibular anterior were missing anterior guidance was established simultaneously avoiding any kind of abnormality due to overjet, overbite or parafunctional habits.

Conclusion:

Porcelain laminate veneers offer a convenient and aesthetically pleasing option for closing midline diastema and spaces in anterior region for enhancing smiles by working closely with the skilled cosmetic dentist. Patients can achieve the beautiful results they desire in a relatively short period. Whether seeking a subtle improvement or a dramatic transformation, veneers provide a versatile solution for addressing spaces between teeth and achieving a confident, radiant smile.

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Figure 1: Pre-operative extraoral photographs

Figure 2: Pre-operative intraoral photographs

Figure 3: Mock-up preparation and Diagnostic Wax-up

Figure 4: Putty index

Figure 5: Orientation and Depth grooves

Figure 6: Enamel Reduction

Figure 7: Final Preparation

Figure 8: Temporisation

Figure 9: Gingival retraction and Final impression

Figure 10: Etching with 10% hydrofluoric acid

Figure 11: Silane coupling agent application

Figure 12: Application of 37% Phosphoric acid

Figure 13: Application of Bonding agent

Figure 14:Final placement of veneers

Intraoral pre-operative and post-operative

Extraoral pre-operative and post-operative